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List of abbreviations

CSV	Comma-separated values
dBM	Digital Biomarker
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EHR	Electronic Health Record
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HC	Healthy control group
HCP	Healthcare professionals
HTTPs	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
N/A	Not available
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
PD	Parkinson's Disease
RBD	REM behaviour disorder
RDM	Research Data Management
SFTP	Secure Shell File Transfer Protocol
SNP	Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms
TLS	Transport Layer Security
UDPRS	Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This document presents the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) crafted by the AI-PROGNOSIS project partners under the EU Horizon Europe RIA program (Grant Agreement No 101080581). It outlines the data collection and processing plans, the compliance with the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable (FAIR) principles, and the data storage and access procedures. Additionally, it provides an estimate of the resources needed for FAIR compliance and addresses legal and ethical considerations concerning the data. The DMP is a living document and will be updated throughout the project duration using the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ARGOS service to continuously meet the project requirements.

1 Introduction

This document serves as the initial version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the Horizon Europe AI-PROGNOSIS project. It aims to detail the type, size, and format of data anticipated to be used and collected during the project. Moreover, the DMP is dedicated to ensuring the alignment of data management with the FAIR principles. The plan also delineates data handling methodologies from inception to potential post-project utilisation, emphasising protection against unsanctioned or inappropriate use.

The core objectives of this DMP version are:

1. Elaborate on the data management lifecycle for anticipated data.
2. Showcase the approach to maintain FAIR principles.
3. Give in-depth description about the expected data types and their management during the project and post-project.
4. Outline methods to grant open access and searchability to stakeholders.
5. Describe project resources necessary for FAIR compliance.

Given the AI-PROGNOSIS project's engagement with human participants, it will oversee personal and sensitive data. The project pledges unwavering compliance with all pertinent national, EU, and international regulations for conducting research with human participants and the protection of personal data.

1.1 Document scope

This document constitutes the preliminary edition of the DMP developed within the scope of the Horizon Europe AI-PROGNOSIS project, designated as deliverable D1.2 “Data Management Plan (initial version)” and is submitted in Month 6. It precedes the deliverable D1.6 “Data Management Plan (final version)”, scheduled for submission in Month 48, which will delineate the definite strategy for the DMP. Both documents are integral to Task 1.4 “Ethics, Legal, and Data Management” under WP1 “Management and Coordination”.

The aim of this document is to devise the inaugural version of the DMP, elucidating the methodologies for the management, storage, and dissemination of data used and collected during the AI-PROGNOSIS project. The DMP encapsulates a comprehensive framework for data management that will be deployed during the project's tenure and offers a set of directives for:

- **Data Collection:** Detailing the methodologies and instruments employed to accumulate data, categorise the data types acquired, and documenting the collection protocols adhered to.
- **Data Storage:** Describing the storage systems implemented to preserve the data's confidentiality and retrievability, inclusive of the data redundancy and restoration protocols.
- **Data Sharing:** Outlining the procedures for the distribution of data amongst the project consortium and external entities, inclusive of the general public as appropriate. This also encompasses measures to safeguard data privacy and adherence to pertinent regulations.
- **Data Preservation:** Addressing the strategies for the sustainable conservation of data, ensuring the maintenance of data veracity and availability in the long run.

The DMP is a living document and will undergo periodic revisions during the project lifecycle to mirror any modifications in data management strategies or compliance obligations. While a component of WP1, this deliverable incorporates contributions from all consortium members and aligns with other work packages tasked with data generation or analysis and, more specifically, with WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP5.

1.2 Document structure

This document is structured into eight principal sections, complemented by an Appendix. Section 1 presents an overview of the data management plan and delineates its scope. Section 2 outlines the guiding principles that will shape the DMP of the AI-PROGNOSIS project. Section 3 details the datasets that will be used and collected during the project, providing insights into their nature, volume, and file formats. Section 4 describes the planned approach to ensure the project-generated datasets conform to the FAIR principles and Section 5 outlines other research outputs. Section 6 details the resource allocation for data collection efforts, while Section 7 lays out the protocols to safeguard the data against unauthorised access. Section 8 discusses the ethical and legal considerations pertaining to the data handling. The document concludes with an Appendix that includes the specific DMP template utilised to garner input from the consortium partners of the AI-PROGNOSIS project for the formulation of the initial DMP version.

2 Principles of the AI-PROGNOSIS data management plan

The Data Management Plan serves as a comprehensive framework for the pseudonymisation, exchange, and dissemination of data used and amassed during the project. The datasets that will be exploited during the AI-PROGNOSIS project range from demographic, genetic and clinical information of individuals to sensor data and user-reported information from digital devices to user-research and software usability data. The largest corpus of data will be used to develop and benchmark AI models for dynamic Parkinson's Disease (PD) symptom screening and for prediction of disease risk, progression and response to PD-specific medication. Given that AI-PROGNOSIS involves the collection of data from human subjects, it includes sensitive personal information, such as health data. Sensitive data, in the context of AI-PROGNOSIS, may include inter alia, demographics (age, sex, education, occupation), year of first symptom, year of introduction of antiparkinsonian treatments, PD subtype, DAT-scan results, polysomnography data, and genetic data. Consequently, stringent emphasis is placed on ethical considerations and access constraints pertaining to personal data to ensure adherence to regulations governing sensitive information. Moreover, access to the AI-PROGNOSIS generated data and the release of datasets fall under the umbrella of the Data Management Team of AI-PROGNOSIS (as defined in Deliverable 1.1), who are responsible for ensuring compliance with legal, regulatory, ethical and FAIR principles, in collaboration with each partner's legal department.

In this context, the initial version of the DMP elaborates on the datasets that the project has access or plans to access or generate. For data storage and preservation, a specialised data management infrastructure will be established on an internal centralised cloud-based platform developed by AI-PRONGOSIS partner INTRA, built on Hetzner platform¹. Utilising virtualisation and orchestration technologies, as well as data back-ups and recovery functions

¹ www.hetzner.com

will permit reliability and security-by-design, while ensuring a secure repository for the data in alignment with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other relevant standards. Informed consent from clinical study participants will be sought and obtained prior any data collection, authorising the collection and processing of their data. Clinical data will be centralised on the fit-for-purpose OpenClinica² platform, also installed on the Hetzner platform, accessible exclusively by authorised study personnel. The data collection methodologies will be subject to approval by the ethics committees or institutional review boards of each participating clinical site (partners CHUT, KCL, TUD, FIN) prior to the commencement of the clinical studies, which will be conducted in four countries, i.e., UK, France, Germany, and Spain.

Additionally, datasets from partners' previous European research and innovation projects, such as the Horizon 2020 i-PROGNOSIS³, and third-party datasets, such as the PPMI⁴ and LIXIPARK⁵, will serve to train the AI models that AI-PROGNOSIS aims to develop.

Open access to data generated by the project will be contingent on its sensitivity level, with certain datasets being made publicly accessible post-pseudonymisation in data repositories (Zenodo⁶), while sensitive data will remain confidential with access strictly controlled or prohibited for external parties.

Finally, the DMP will be maintained using the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ARGOS⁷ service. This approach will streamline the DMP's formulation and upkeep and enhance the alignment of data sharing practices with the FAIR principles and GDPR compliance.

3 Data Summary

The AI-PROGNOSIS project aims to deliver a digital health ecosystem for persons with and without PD and relevant healthcare professionals, enabling dynamic PD screening, disease progression monitoring, and medication response optimisation, through novel predictive models and digital biomarkers (dBMs).

To this end, the project will exploit and collect a variety of in-depth health, lifestyle, smartphone/wearable sensor, and genetic data to:

- Detect REM behaviour disorder (RBD), daytime somnolence, as well as motor and cognitive function and symptoms
- Create genetic profiles that will enhance PD risk assessment and disease prognosis
- Develop trustworthy AI models for PD risk, PD progression and PD-specific medication response

The final outcome will be a validated (via proof-of-concept), privacy-aware, trustworthy AI-enabled toolkit providing 1) healthcare professionals with actionable and explainable data for effective PD risk assessment, monitoring, and treatment decision support and 2) individuals with or without PD with personalised insights for informed health management in collaboration with their attending physicians.

² <https://www.openclinica.com/>

³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/690494>

⁴ <https://www.ppmi-info.org/>

⁵ <https://parkinson.network/en/clinical-study/lixipark>

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/>

⁷ <https://argos.opensaire.eu/splash/>

In particular, within the AI-PROGNOSIS project, a diverse spectrum of data will be harnessed to foster an all-encompassing understanding of the disease and its progression, combining:

- **Clinical, demographic and lifestyle data:** Comprehensive patient records, medical histories, clinical findings, and other pertinent health information will be crucial for pinpointing primary PD indicators and crafting prognostic models.
- **Blood samples and DNA data:** Blood samples and extracted DNA from PD cases and control individuals, to genotype PD cases and control samples at selected single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) and use the generated data as input to AI-PROGNOSIS predictive models.
- **Imaging data:** DaTSCANS will be performed to individuals and will be used to validate the performance of the PD risk predictive model in a dedicated study of the project.
- **Digital phenotyping data:** Continuous, passive data collected from the smartphone and a wrist wearable will be leveraged to develop dBMs for monitoring key PD risk and progression indicators in daily life.
- **Body tracking data:** AI-PROGNOSIS will leverage skeleton tracked data of individuals, captured from smartphone cameras, performing specific items from Movement Disorder Society-Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS) part III, to estimate balance/posture scores.
- **User research and usability data** will be collected during user research activities, co-creation workshops and clinical studies to shape the features of the AI-PROGNOSIS tools and evaluate their usability.

The collected data will undergo pseudonymisation to uphold privacy standards and will be instrumental in shaping the AI-PROGNOSIS digital health ecosystem.

3.1 List of datasets

In this section, we present an epitomised description of the datasets that will be collected during the AI-PROGNOSIS project, as well as of the third-party datasets that will be exploited by the project, along with information on the file types, the (expected) volume of the dataset, and the main responsible partner for handling. The volume of data to be collected by the project cannot be determined accurately and thus an estimate is provided. In the following, N/A stands for 'not available'.

3.1.1 Third-party datasets

In this section we describe third-party datasets that were accessed by consortium partners for the research and development needs of the project.

Dataset #1: i-PROGNOSIS typing dataset		
Description: Keystroke timing and pressure data that correspond to short text excerpts typed by early Parkinson's disease (PD) patients (n=18) and healthy controls (n=15) on a common touchscreen-equipped smartphone, using a custom virtual keyboard, in a controlled laboratory environment.		
File types: .txt	Size: 1.2 MB	Responsible partner(s): AUTH

Dataset #2: REAL-PD IMU smartwatch data		
Description: REAL-PD contains accelerometer and gyroscope data (from smartwatch and smartphone) and severity scores for tremor, dyskinesias and ON/OFF medication status. Symptoms are reported through 20-minute interval reports.		
File types: .csv	Size: 12 GB	Responsible partner(s): CERTH

Dataset #3: MJFF Levodopa Wearable Sensors Dataset		
Description: The dataset comprises accelerometer data collected in the laboratory with ground truth labels of symptom severity during the performance of scripted motor tasks as well as wearable sensor data collected in the home setting during the performance of unscripted motor tasks.		
File types: .csv, .txt	Size: 68.5 GB	Responsible partner(s): CERTH

Dataset #4: CIS-PD IMU smartwatch data		
Description: CIS-PD contains accelerometer data and severity scores for tremor, dyskinesias and ON/OFF medication status. Symptoms are reported through 30-minute interval reports.		
File types: .csv	Size: 3.6 GB	Responsible partner(s): CERTH

Dataset #5: i-PROGNOSIS iMAT Assessment Tests dataset		
Description: This dataset evaluates the effectiveness of the i-PROGNOSIS body tracking-based intelligent Motor Assessment Tests (iMAT) in accurately reflecting the motor skill status of PD patients; and potential for further enhancing iMAT with machine learning techniques to infer the stage of PD patients more efficiently.		
File types: .json, .csv	Size: 100 MB	Responsible partner(s): FMH, AUTH

Dataset #6: COPPADIS-15 cohort		
Description: Observational descriptive longitudinal study. Clinical and demographic data. Comparison with healthy controls. Motor, non-motor symptoms, biomarkers and imaging data.		
File types: .sav	Size: 4.3 MB	Responsible partner(s): FIN

Dataset #7: PPMI database		
Description: Clinical and longitudinal measurements (omics, clinical assessments, imaging (DaTSCAN), demographics and lifestyle) for more than 1,700 individuals from multiple cohorts of interest (e.g., clinically diagnosed PD, non-manifest gene carriers, healthy controls, and prodromal). A subset includes sensor data from smartwatch (Verily study) and smartphone (Roche study).		
File types: .csv, .json	Size: ~10 GB (>200 TB with omics, imaging, Verily and Roche datasets)	Responsible partner(s): FIN

Dataset #8: LIXIPARK trial		
Description: The data were collected in the framework of LIXIPARK, a multicenter, randomised, placebo-controlled, double-blind, parallel-group study of lixisenatide in 156 patients with early Parkinson's disease (PD) (78 on placebo, 78 on lixisenatide). It was run at 21 centers of the French		

NS-Park/FCRIN network. Patients with early PD (< 3 years since diagnosis) on stable symptomatic medications and without motor complications were randomised to receive subcutaneous injections of placebo or 20 µg lixisenatide once daily for 12 months, followed by a 2-month wash-out period. The primary endpoint was the change from baseline to month-12 in the MDS-UPDRS part III (motor examination) score in the ON condition.

File types: .csv	Size: N/A	Responsible partner(s): CHUT
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Dataset #9: RBD-Czech

Description: High resolution actigraphic recording (MotionWatch, CamNtech Ltd.) and confirming polysomnographic recording. The actigraphy data are stored in .txt files. The data will be used to identify/classify patients with RBD.

File types: .txt	Size: 158 MB	Responsible partner(s): KUL
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Dataset #10: UK Biobank

Description: Extensive phenotypic and genotypic data (from questionnaires, physical measures, sample assays, accelerometry, multimodal imaging, genome-wide genotyping, and longitudinal follow-up for a wide range of health-related outcomes) from more than 500,000 individuals, including PD patients and incident PD diagnoses, in the UK.

File types: various, mainly .csv	Size: N/A	Responsible partner(s): AUTH
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Dataset #11: AMP PD cohorts

Description: Clinical and omics (transcriptomic, genomic, proteomic, and single nucleus brain data) data from eight unified cohorts (BioFIND, HBS, LBD, LCC, PDBP, PPMI, STEADY-PD3 and SURE-PD3) including over 10,000 participants.

File types: various, mainly .csv	Size: N/A	Responsible partner(s): CING
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3.1.2 AI-PROGNOSIS generated datasets

As AI-PROGNOSIS generated datasets, we consider the data that will be collected in the framework of the project, and specifically, during the dBM-DEV, AI-PRA and AI-PMP studies, as well as the user research and co-creation activities of the project.

Dataset #12: AI-PRA genetic analysis data

Description: SNP data will be collected from 100 participants during the AI-PRA study to genotype new PD cases and control samples at selected SNPs and use the generated data for the AI-PROGNOSIS developed PD risk prediction model.

File types: .xlsx, .csv	Size: ~50 GB	Responsible partner(s): CING
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Dataset #13: AI-PMP genetic analysis data

Description: SNP data will be collected from 100 participants during the AI-PMP study to genotype new PD cases and control samples at selected SNPs and use the generated data for the AI-PROGNOSIS developed PD progression and medication response prediction models.

File types: .xlsx, .csv	Size: ~50 GB	Responsible partner(s): CING
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Dataset #14: dBM-DEV study typing dataset		
Description: Keystroke dynamics-related data collected during routine touchscreen typing in daily living using a custom virtual keyboard from 60 participants comprising the development and confirmation cohort during the dBM-DEV study.		
File types: .json	Size: ~60 MB	Responsible partner(s): AUTH

Dataset #15: AI-PRA study typing dataset		
Description: Keystroke dynamics-related data collected during routine touchscreen typing in daily living using a custom virtual keyboard from a sample of 100 participants without diagnosed PD enriched with cases of increased risk of having prodromal PD.		
File types: .json	Size: ~400 MB	Responsible partner(s): AUTH

Dataset #16: AI-PMP study typing dataset		
Description: Keystroke dynamics-related data collected during routine touchscreen typing in daily living using a custom virtual keyboard from 100 participants with PD during the AI-PMP study.		
File types: .json	Size: ~400 MB	Responsible partner(s): AUTH

Dataset #17: dBM-DEV study IMU smartwatch data		
Description: It will contain all day IMU data from smartwatch as well as estimations on motor function from the validated dBM, from 90 participants (development and confirmation cohort) in the dBM-DEV study.		
File types: .csv	Size: ~700 GB	Responsible partner(s): CERTH, KUL

Dataset #18: AI-PRA study IMU smartwatch data		
Description: It will contain all day IMU data from smartwatch as well as estimations on motor function from the validated dBM, from 100 participants in the AI-PRA study.		
File types: .csv	Size: ~5 TB	Responsible partner(s): CERTH, KUL

Dataset #19: AI-PMP study IMU smartwatch data		
Description: It will contain all day IMU data from smartwatch as well as estimations on motor function from the validated dBM, from 100 participants in the AI-PMP study.		
File types: .csv	Size: ~5 TB	Responsible partner(s): CERTH, KUL

Dataset #20: dBM-DEV study cognitive function data		
Description: It will contain user-smartphone interaction data (swipes, taps, and keystroke events), as well as scores from active cognitive tests from 60 participants (confirmation cohort) in the of dBM-DEV study.		
File types: .csv	Size: ~60 MB	Responsible partner(s): CERTH

Dataset #21: AI-PRA study cognitive function data		
Description: It will contain user-smartphone interaction data (swipes, taps, and keystroke events), as well as scores from active cognitive tests from 100 participants in the AI-PRA study.		
File types: .csv	Size: ~400 MB	Responsible partner(s): CERTH

Dataset #22: AI-PMP study cognitive function data		
Description: It will contain user-smartphone interaction data (swipes, taps, and keystroke events), as well as scores from active cognitive tests from 100 participants in the AI-PMP study		
File types: .csv	Size: ~400 MB	Responsible partner(s): CERTH

Dataset #23: dBM-DEV study skeleton tracking dataset for balance/posture assessment		
Description: Skeleton tracked data from the 60 participants (confirmation cohort) of the dBM-DEV study, captured from smartphones, performing specific items from MDS-UPDRS part III, along with the corresponding scores.		
File types: .json, .mp4, .csv	Size: ~10 GB	Responsible partner(s): FMH

Dataset #24: AI-PRA study skeleton tracking dataset for balance/posture assessment		
Description: Skeleton tracked data from the 100 participants of the AI-PRA study, captured from smartphones, performing specific items from MDS-UPDRS part III, along with the corresponding scores.		
File types: .json, .mp4, .csv	Size: ~50 GB	Responsible partner(s): FMH

Dataset #25: AI-PMP study skeleton tracking dataset for balance/posture assessment		
Description: Skeleton tracked data from the 100 participants of the AI-PMP study, captured from smartphones, performing specific items from MDS-UPDRS part III, along with the corresponding scores.		
File types: .json, .mp4, .csv	Size: ~50 GB	Responsible partner(s): FMH

Dataset #26: Clinical data from the digital biomarkers development, validation and verification study (dBM-DEV study)		
Description: These are clinical data from an open label cross-sectional observational study to be obtained from 90 subjects recruited in Germany, France, UK and Spain. Patients' clinical assessment will include demographics (age, sex, education, handedness), year of first symptom, year of introduction of antiparkinsonian treatments and PD subtype. Moreover, data from the following clinical scales will be obtained: MDS-UPDRS, MoCA, PDQ-8, RBDSQ and ESS.		
File types: .csv	Size: ~10 MB	Responsible partner(s): CHUT, TUD, KCL, FIN

Dataset #27: Clinical data from the Artificial intelligence-based Parkinson's risk assessment study (AI-PRA study)		
Description: These are clinical data from a proof of concept, multi-centre, observational, cohort study with single blinded rater recruiting 100 participants without PD in France, UK and Spain (and possibly also Germany, TBC). Persons' clinical assessment will include demographics, medical history and medical examination, medication, BMI, UPSIT, UPDRS, ESS, LSBP, NMSS, MoCA,		

HADS, PDQ-39, PGI-S, CGI, patients satisfaction scale, HP satisfaction questionnaire, usability and use of app and sensors compliance.

File types: .csv	Size: ~10 MB	Responsible partner(s): CHUT, KCL, FIN
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Dataset #28: Clinical data from the AI-based progression and medication response prediction study (AI-PMP study)

Description: These are clinical data from a proof-of-concept, multi-centre, low-interventional, randomised, controlled open-label parallel group study recruiting 100 participants in France, UK, Germany and Spain. Patients' clinical assessment will include demographics, medical history and medical examination, concomitant medication, MDS-UPDRS, PDQ-39, patients satisfaction scale, usability and use of app and sensors compliance.

File types: .csv	Size: ~10 MB	Responsible partner(s): CHUT, KCL, FIN
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Dataset #29: DaTSCAN data in the AI-PRA study

Description: These are single photon emission computed tomography data quantifying dopamine transporter availability in the 100 participants of the AI-PRA study.

File types: .DICOM	Size: ~1 GB	Responsible partner(s): CHUT, KCL, FIN
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Dataset #30: Polysomnography data collected in the dBM-DEV study

Description: These are polysomnography data collected from 60 participants in the confirmation cohort of the dBM-Dev study.

File types: .csv	Size: ~2 GB	Responsible partner(s): CHUT, TUD, KCL, FIN
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Dataset #31: AI-PROGNOSIS generated RBD data in the dBM-DEV study

Description: RBD data (log information) from the 90 participants (development and confirmation cohort) of the dBM-DEV study will be collected and used to design and evaluate the Digital biomarkers in the identification of RBD and daytime somnolence.

File types: .json	Size: ~5 MB	Responsible partner(s): KUL
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Dataset #32: AI-PROGNOSIS generated RBD data in the AI-PRA study

Description: RBD and daytime somnolence data (log information) from the 100 participants of the AI-PRA study will be collected and used by the AI-PROGNOSIS PD risk assessment AI model, with the goal to accomplish the objectives of AI-PRA study.

File types: .json	Size: ~50 MB	Responsible partner(s): KUL
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Dataset #33: AI-PROGNOSIS generated RBD data in the AI-PMP study

Description: RBD data (log information) from the 100 participants of the AI-PMP study will be collected, to passively track known progression of RBD and daytime somnolence.

File types: .json	Size: ~50 MB	Responsible partner(s): KUL
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Dataset #34: mAI-Health mobile app user research data		
Description: Results from surveys, panels and other qualitative interactions that will be conducted with stakeholders such as patients, caregivers and similar. Data are processed to understand stakeholder perspectives, values, and preferences, which will be used in developing guidelines for ethical development and implementation of AI tools for risk assessment, diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment management in Parkinson's Disease.		
File types: .docx, .pdf, .xlsx	Size: ~10 MB	Responsible partner(s): UU

Dataset #35: mAI-Health mobile app usability data		
Description: SUS (System Usability Scale) scores from moderated and unmoderated/remote and in person usability testing with participants of co-creation workshops and the AI-PRA study. Scores from moderated and unmoderated/remote and in person user satisfaction questionnaires. Participants consist of app users.		
File types: .docx, .pdf, .xlsx	Size: ~10 MB	Responsible partner(s): UU

Dataset #36: mAI-Care mobile app user research data		
Description: Results from surveys, panels and other qualitative interactions that will be conducted with stakeholders such as patients, caregivers and similar. Data are processed to understand stakeholder perspectives, values, and preferences, which will be used in developing guidelines for ethical development and implementation of AI tools for risk assessment, diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment management in Parkinson's Disease.		
File types: .docx, .pdf, .xlsx	Size: ~10 MB	Responsible partner(s): UU

Dataset #37: mAI-Care mobile app usability data		
Description: SUS (System Usability Scale) scores from moderated and unmoderated usability testing with participants of co-creation workshops and the AI-PMP study. Scores of user satisfaction questionnaires. Participants consist of app users.		
File types: .docx, .pdf, .xlsx	Size: ~10 MB	Responsible partner(s): UU

Dataset #38: mAI-Insights web app usability data		
Description: SUS (System Usability Scale) scores from moderated and unmoderated usability testing with healthcare professionals of co-creation workshops and the AI-PRA/AI-PMP studies. Scores of user satisfaction questionnaires. Participants consist of health care professionals.		
File types: .docx, .pdf, .xlsx	Size: ~10 MB	Responsible partner(s): UU

3.2 File type description

Mostly common file types, such as Comma-Separated Values (CSV), JavaScript Object Notation (JSON), MPEG-4 Part 14 (MP4), will be used for all datasets collected during the AI-PROGNOSIS project, if applicable, to ensure maximum accessibility, interoperability, and reusability according to the FAIR principles. In addition, the use of common file types enables

full compatibility with popular software, thus allowing the use and processing of the collected data during the lifecycle of the project and even after the end of the project.

Finally, a common data model based on the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) or the Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) standard will be used for certain data types that will be collected by the project. In this way, the AI-PROGNOSIS project will ensure that the collected health data are standardised, easily accessible, and reusable.

4 FAIR data

Proper Research Data Management (RDM)⁸ is mandatory for any Horizon Europe project generating or reusing research data. It is a key part of Horizon Europe's open science requirements and states that beneficiaries must manage the digital research data generated in a project responsibly, in line with the FAIR principles, to stimulate knowledge acquisition and innovation.

The FAIR data strategy is encapsulated by its acronym:

- **Findable data:** Implementing straightforward naming and versioning systems for data and metadata, integrating search keywords and utilising digital object identifiers (DOIs).
- **Accessible data:** Outlining methods for data availability and specifying tools necessary for data access.
- **Interoperable data:** Employing standards and vocabularies for metadata and data types.
- **Reusable data:** Detailing the period during which data will be available and setting licensing conditions for data.

For this project, all collected data from research participants will be pseudonymised, ensuring that no personal data relating to identifiable individuals or research participants is disclosed publicly.

Additionally, given that the project deals with Sensitive data, it's important to evaluate the risks associated with each type of data before deciding on their public disclosure. Particularly, the feasibility of re-identifying research participants by integrating other data sets should be considered. Therefore, the Data Management Team of AI-PROGNOSIS will review the release of each AI-PROGNOSIS generated dataset, make sure that it follows the FAIR principles and, in collaboration with the legal departments of each involved partner, ensure that they comply with legal regulatory and ethical guidelines.

4.1 Findable data

The pseudonymised version of the data collected in this project will be identified by a persistent identifier. This identifier will be a study id for the clinical data, while for the smartwatch and smartphone data, the identifier will be the study id and the participant id. This procedure will ensure that all data are de-identified. Both study id and participant id will be registered in the mAI-Health and mAI-Care apps at the time of participant recruitment, during which the participants download and install the app in their smartphones and fill in the study id and participant id that will be provided by the recruiter to a dedicated screen. The identifier will be applied to link the user with the data collected, but no other identifiers will be used or stored

⁸ Horizon Europe mandate for RDM: <https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-comply-with-horizon-europe-mandate-for-rdm>

that may lead to user identification. The key tables for the de-identified data will be held by the study team of each clinical site that may provide limited access to other users. Pseudonymisation techniques may be implemented after the end of the project, but this is not guaranteed. Therefore, a persistent identifier, with access to some additional information, could identify the data.

Rich metadata (i.e., textual description of data, timestamps, data structure, etc.), excluding personal data, will be provided to facilitate discovery, identification and detailed description of the data produced. Each record contains a minimum of DataCite's⁹ mandatory terms, with optionally additional DataCite recommended terms and Zenodo's enrichments. In addition, search keywords will be provided in the metadata to optimise the possibility for discovery and potential re-use. These keywords will be mostly related to data protection law. The metadata will be indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing. Metadata of each record is sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there. The metadata will comply with the Open Archives Initiative's Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) and will be searchable via the OpenAIRE catalogue and Zenodo, both of which support web-based search. Finally, the aim is to ensure that the metadata is as accessible and usable as possible.

4.2 Accessible data

The project ensures that data is deposited in a platform built on the Zenodo infrastructure that is hosted by CERN and supports back up, has data security mechanisms in place and follows repository and metadata standards.

Clinical partners will use local infrastructures/servers for data collection and storage, while copies of the clinical data will be securely transferred to the internal centralised cloud-based platform developed by INTRA. Regarding the User Research data and metadata, the controller (UU) will be storing the data in an encrypted set of digital files, via the data service UIT Data storage/Argos. Data from wearable sensors (i.e., smart watch, smartphone) will be collected via the mAI-Health and mAI-Care apps and then transferred to the internal cloud infrastructure. Data collected within the project will be released to the Zenodo open repository (part of OpenAIRE¹⁰ and of the re3data.org registry¹¹). The data will be erased from the smartphone upon successful transfer or if the application is uninstalled. Moreover, identifiers will be assigned to the data, probably DOI. All data communication will be encrypted, and security measures are in place for data security at the platform. Data lineage is always clear and each of the partners that work with data have security measures in place that prohibited unauthorised use of the data.

The AI-PROGNOSIS project will ensure restricted access to sensitive data, as well as deliverables with private or sensitive content, while the rest of the data (to be shared as public datasets if deemed feasible by the Data Management Team) and the produced content of the AI-PROGNOSIS project will be made publicly available to promote research and innovation.

In cases where an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of intellectual property, the maximum duration of the embargo period is set to 24 months for the publication. This period might be extended in the case of the patent, when the additional delay of 18 months has to be applied from the patent filing date. After this period, the data will be processed, analysed, and published as soon as possible. Access to the data will be possible

⁹ <https://schema.datacite.org/>

¹⁰ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

¹¹ <https://www.re3data.org/>

through authentication mechanisms that ensure role-based access control, while a free and standardised access protocol will be provided, where possible. For private and sensitive data, access will be provided to authorised users only and user authentication mechanisms and interfaces for secure data exchange will be provided and put in place.

Metadata will be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement. These metadata will contain information to enable the user to access the data and they will be findable for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least, as well as an extended period, which is determined by each responsible partner individually. After the end of the project, CHUT is required to store data and metadata for 15 years, FIN for 25 years, KCL for 5 years, TUD for 15 years and UU for 10 years. For all data packets stored in the repository, a complete set of metadata will be provided and stored. The metadata will also accompany each data packet in the data repository where it is stored. All data will be accessible by several open-source editors and the relevant documentation will be provided. This ensures that the data is not only accessible but also usable, as users will have the necessary tools and information to interpret and work with the data.

4.3 Interoperable data

The project will use various data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats, and methodologies to ensure data interoperability. For metadata, Zenodo uses JSON Schema for metadata representation and also offers exports to formats like Dublin Core or MARCXML. Zenodo refers to open vocabularies such as Open Definition, FundRef, and OpenAIRE for certain terms. All AI-PROGNOSIS partners agreed on the development of a common data model based on the OMOP or FHIR standard to describe the data and metadata. Thus, interoperability will be facilitated by adopting standard formats and units of measure widely used in the community and by providing proper documentation in terms of Readme files. Data harmonisation will be led by partner INTRA (Task 2.4) on the internal cloud infrastructure. In the case of data transfer from applications to the central cloud data management system, secure protocols like Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS)/ Transport Layer Security (TLS) or Secure Shell File Transfer Protocol (SFTP) will be employed, with the exact design of the interfaces and standards applied currently under discussion.

The current plan is to use existing ontologies and vocabularies, when possible, which will ensure that the data is compatible with other datasets and can be easily understood and used by others in the field. Each referenced external piece of metadata will be qualified by a resolvable Uniform Resource Locator (URL). The data packets produced are self-contained and are fully described by the associated metadata. Proper citation of the data is ensured by the citation text, as well as a unique DOI number, provided for each data packet, which is also provided at the repository, in which the data resides.

4.4 Re-usable data

The AI-PROGNOSIS project will ensure that a comprehensive documentation of the data is provided to facilitate data re-use. This documentation will include Readme files, variable definitions, units of measurement and other relevant information. The exact form of documentation will be decided in the future, but it will likely include details on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses and more. Part of the documentation might also be written in the corresponding deliverable of each work package of the project.

The AI-PROGNOSIS project has varying levels of data availability for re-use based on the nature of the data. Non-sensitive, pseudonymised data that will be derived from the clinical

studies (such as skeletal and accelerometer data) will be made freely available in the public domain by depositing data and associated metadata to Zenodo, under Creative Commons Zero (CC0), except for cases that adhere to privacy, confidentiality and security rules. On the other hand, private and sensitive data will offer restricted access and the data licencing approach will be decided at a later stage of the project. The type of license, if any, will be decided in accordance with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement. The project will thoroughly document the provenance of the data using appropriate standards. Data and metadata uploaded to Zenodo are traceable to a registered user, and metadata can describe the original authors of the published work.

During the project, the Data Management Team, along with the Project Coordinator and the partners concerned will be responsible for the data sharing and usage. Data access governance after the project will be specified by the end of the second year of the project and will be reported in the final version of the DMP. In any case, the option and purpose of reusing data collected from clinical study participants will be clearly stated in the informed consent.

The infrastructure provided by INTRA, will ensure that versioning is supported. In this way, the origin and lifecycle of the data are clearly defined, enhancing the data re-usability. Finally, all partners will process and publish data according to FAIR principles and best practice guidelines. After the project, periodic quality assessment procedures will take place to ensure the ongoing integrity and usability of the data. These processes will ensure that the data remains reliable, accurate and suitable for re-use over time.

5 Other research outputs

Other research outputs in the AI-PROGNOSIS include blood samples that will be collected by the involved clinical sites in France, UK, and Spain by partners CHUT, KCL, and FIN respectively, as well as DNA code information that will be gathered by CING in Cyprus. The goal of these outputs is to genotype new PD cases and control samples at selected SNPs. Any changes will be reflected in the next version of DMP D1.6-Data Management Plan (final version) in month 48.

6 Allocation of resources

There are no costs associated in making data or other research outputs FAIR. Created datasets will be uploaded to Zenodo, which is a freely accessible repository of data that follows FAIR guidelines. In addition, a cost estimate associated with data storage and infrastructure setup on the Hetzner cloud provider has been provided in accordance with the requirements of the Grant Agreement under the partner INTRA (refer to Grant Agreement – Annex 2).

Regarding data curation, processing and storage, each partner that collects data will be responsible for assigning a Data Protection Officer (DPO) that will oversee that the gathered data are compliant to EU directives 2016/679 and EU 2016/680 on the processing of personal data.

7 Data security and protection

Any gathered data will be securely handled throughout the entire duration of AI-PROGNOSIS so as to protect it from loss and unauthorised access. All data will be pseudonymised, meaning

that each patient will be represented by a study id, making it impossible to be identified and/or mapped to their data.

The AI-PROGNOSIS data management services support a centralised cloud-based deployment, utilising virtualisation and orchestration technologies that permit reliability and security-by-design, as well as numerous data back-up and recovery functions.

The operating system of the Virtual Machines hosting the various components and data is planned to undergo standard server hardening methods. In addition, a user authentication and authorisation mechanism will be employed. Examples of security precautions to be employed include: deactivation of SSH remote connections with a method other than public/private key authentication, deactivation of “root” user, limitation of IPs with permission to access the infrastructure via firewalls, adoption of policies for creation of secure passwords and use of encrypted and password protected physical disks (if needed). Last, the data management infrastructure in the cloud ensures compliance with GDPR. For data transfer, secure protocols like HTTPS/TLS or SFTP will be employed.

The AI-PROGNOSIS partners will ensure that the data remains protected under all necessary security controls (including backup policies and integrity checks) and access controls (identification, authentication, authorisation). In the unfortunate event of personal data breach, each of the clinical sites will follow the procedure for data breaches as given by their institutions. Such a procedure includes the notification of the department head or supervisor, the notification of the data subject(s) that may have been affected by the breach, the creation of an internal report that documents the type and content of data that have been compromised and the notification of concerned consortium members.

Regarding long-term data preservation and curation, each partner producing data will be responsible to develop their own strategy for handling the data after the end of the project, since these data will be stored in institutional archives. More specifically, CHUT is required to store data and metadata for 15 years from the end of the clinical study and backed up on local servers of the University Hospital of Toulouse with controlled access. On the other hand, FIN will preserve data and metadata for 25 years at the Hospital Ruber Internacional after the end of the clinical trial, while KCL and the associated UK hospitals and TUD in Germany will preserve data and metadata for 5 and 15 years, respectively.

8 Ethical and legal aspects

Since the AI-PROGNOSIS project is concerned with the collection of private and sensitive data, such as personal information, medical records from patients with PD and unaffected controls, ethical and legal aspects arise that will be dealt by the partners of the project accordingly. Task T1.4 “Ethics, legal and data management”, led by partner DBC, is dedicated to identifying and formulating the key ethical (for healthcare and clinical research) and legal (focusing on data protection, FAIR principles, and GDPR) requirements that are pertinent to the project and will govern its activities, including the development of the digital health ecosystem and the design and execution of clinical studies.

Specifically, prospective study participants will be approached by the study team, be provided with a participant information sheet, and asked whether they want to participate. If they agree they sign the consent form and they can receive a signed copy of the consent form. The consent form will be created in local languages relevant to each hospital location. Prior to the participation, each prospective participant will be kindly asked to read the patient information sheet that includes information on data storage, privacy and participant rights and sign the

informed consent form on whether they agree with data collection, processing and preservation and after given enough time to consider all given information. Contact information of the study site and research team for questions or complaints will also be included. The information sheet and the consent form will be made available in this document as soon as possible.

The participants will be able to indicate whether they agree with the study or not, and if they refuse to participate, their data will not be collected. Automatic data collection on digital parameters can be controlled from the mAI-Health and mAI-Care mobile app. Clinical and biological data are collected physically, and questionnaires are provided digitally, therefore participants have control on what data to provide. Participants are informed that they have the right to withdraw at any moment of data collection. When a participant withdraws consent, the data collected up to the moment of withdrawal will be used (according to GDPR/AVG Article 89(1)), but no further data will be collected. Participants can request their own data by contacting the research team. Upon request, the identity of the person will be verified, and the principal investigator will make a data extraction of the participants' data only and will send the data to the participant via an encrypted link using a platform such as SURFfilesender.

Additionally, AI-PROGNOSIS will ensure that the exposed metadata from the collected datasets will not record any restricted information. Finally, the Hetzner cloud infrastructure that will store and manage the generated datasets of the AI-PROGNOSIS project offers a Data Processing Protection Agreement that can ensure the GDPR compliance, while in M47, before the final platform is released, a privacy statement will be drafted to confirm that data are handled within the appropriate legal framework, including the GDPR.

An ethics and data protection impact assessment will be conducted and reported through deliverables D1.3 and D1.4, in order to assess all the project related activities, identify any possible ethics-related gaps and the necessary measures to be implemented, thus ensuring ethical compliance.

Conclusions

An initial version of the DMP was developed that describes the key datasets that the project accessed or is in the process of accessing (11 datasets) by month 6 (M6), as well as the datasets expected to be generated (27 datasets) by the project, including short descriptions, (expected) volume, and main partner responsible for handling.

The preliminary approach to be adopted for ensuring data adherence to the FAIR principles was presented. The required resources for making data compliant with FAIR sharing were also estimated. Finally, the approach for ethical and legal compliance of data collection activities of the project was epitomised.

This document will be available online using the EOSC ARGOS service that will enable the DMP to be continuously updated during the lifespan of the AI-PROGNOSIS project until the submission of the deliverable D1.6 "Data management plan (final version)" in M48. The next update and refinement of the DMP will take place internally using the EOSC ARGOS service in M28 (internal report) after the end of the user research/co-creation phase and of the first clinical study (dBM-DEV study), during which a first version of the datasets will have been collected and processed and the AI-PROGNOSIS research and development teams will have a good knowledge of the type, volume, and content of data collected.

Appendix I - Horizon Europe Dataset Description Template

Data Summary
1. Dataset name
2. Dataset description
3. Is the described dataset an existing one?
4. What are the types and formats of data in the described dataset?
5. What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
6. What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
7. What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
8. To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?
FAIR data: Making data findable, including provisions for metadata
9. Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
10. Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery?
11. Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimise the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
12. Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?
FAIR data: Making data accessible
Repository
13. Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
14. Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
15. Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?
Data
16. Will all data be made openly available?
17. If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
18. Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?
19. If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
20. How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
21. Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?
Metadata
22. Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

23. How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
24. Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?
FAIR data: Making data interoperable
25. What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
26. In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?
27. Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?
FAIR data: Increase data re-use
28. How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
29. Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
30. Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
31. Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
32. Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
Allocation of resources
33. What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
34. How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
35. Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
36. How will long term preservation be ensured?
Data security
37. What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
38. Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?
Ethics
39. Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?
40. Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?
41. Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?
42. What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?
43. Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Other issues

44. Do you make use of other procedures for data management?
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